

Optimizing care services in Covid-19 ICU in a Lebanese Hospital – Interventional Case Study

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has taken a huge toll on healthcare systems with serious consequences for patients, families and healthcare professionals around the world. Thus, health services in general and intensive care services (ICUs) in particular, will have to quickly adapt to the expected increase in the number of cases. While COVID-19 is an emerging disease, potential vulnerability models and considerations regarding health resilience and service organization to meet the requirements are being discussed. In this environment, innovative approaches to care are likely to be prevalent. This study is about an interventional study, using a mixed method: quantitative and qualitative, specifically designed to assess the immediate impact of treatment or prevention and preparedness measures on this pandemic, with group-wide intervention (ICU staff) using specific tools such as instructional/educational practices and learning strategies that can be used throughout our process. Consequently, we aim to detect the gaps and challenges presented with the aim of evaluating and optimizing those services. In our research, and despite all the stress that faced the staff inside the COVID-19 ICU, we found that the organization have supported its staff and they have maintained together the quality of care by cooperating and well managing the situation over all the sides without denying the improvement of raising patients and staff satisfaction in addition to the recovery rate of infected patients.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	iv
LIST OF FIGURES	v
LIST OF TABLES.....	vi
LIST OF SYMBOLS	vii
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	viii
CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Background.....	1
1.2 Problem Statement.....	2
1.3 Objectives	3
1.4 Outline	3
CHAPTER 2 LITERATURE REVIEW	5
2.1 Introduction	5
2.2 National Lebanese Experience.....	5
2.3 Preparedness and Readiness of an ICU COVID-19	8
2.4 Challenges that Face INTENSIVE Care Units During the Pandemic.....	14
2.5 Potential Interventions	23
2.6 Conclusion	24
CHAPTER 3 RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY.....	25
3.1 Introduction	25
3.2 The COVID Intensive Care Unit In The Hospital	25
3.3 Methodology.....	26
3.4 Population.....	28
3.5 Outcome Indicators.....	28
3.6 Data Collection	30
3.7 Data Analysis.....	31
3.8 Conclusion	31
CHAPTER 4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	32
4.1 Introduction	32
4.2 Results	32
4.3 Discussion.....	55
4.4 Limitation	55
4.5 Conclusion	56
CHAPTER 5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK	57
5.1 Conclusion	57
5.2 Future Work.....	58
REFERENCES	59
APPENDIX A Informed Consent.....	63
APPENDIX B Assessment of Existing Situation	65
APPENDIX C Staff Satisfaction Questionnaire	69

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2-1: ICU model for airborne illness.....	15
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LIST OF TABLES

Table 2-1: Challenges and Recommendations facing the COVID-19 ICU (Infrastructure)....	14
Table 2-2: Challenges and Recommendations facing the COVID-19 ICU (Infection Prevention and Control)	16
Table 2-3: Challenges and Recommendations facing the COVID-19 ICU (ICU Capacity) ...	19
Table 2-4: Challenges and Recommendations facing the COVID-19 ICU (ICU Staffing).....	20
Table 2-5: Challenges and Recommendations facing the COVID-19 ICU (ICU Triage)	21
Table 2-6: Initial approach to critically ill patients with suspected COVID-19	22
Table 3-1: Initial Parameters and Values	29
Table 3-2: Variables and Description	29
Table 4-1: SWOT Analysis of Initial Situation.....	32
Table 4-2: Outcomes' percentage during the pre-interventional assessment.....	38
Table 4-3: COVID-19 ICU patients list	38
Table 4-4: Percentage of Staff Satisfaction (Pre-interventional assessment)	40
Table 4-5: Patient Transport Issues and Solutions for COVID-19	43
Table 4-6: Outcomes' percentage during the post-interventional assessment	52
Table 4-7: Percentage of Staff Satisfaction (Post-interventional assessment).....	53
Table 4-8: Outcomes' percentage during the pre and post-interventional assessment	54

LIST OF SYMBOLS

%: Percentage.

<: Less than.

>: Greater than.

+: Positive.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

- ADL: Activity of Daily Living.
- AGP: Aerosol Generating Procedures.
- AIIR: Airborne Infection Isolation Room.
- ANZICS: Australian and NewZeland Intensive Care Society.
- ARDS: Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome.
- BVM: Bag Valve Mask.
- CDC: Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.
- COVID-19: Corona Virus Disease.
- CO₂: Carbone Dioxide.
- CT-Scan: Computed Tomography – Scan.
- EMD: Emergency Department.
- HCW: Healthcare Worker.
- HEPA: High Efficiency Particulate Air.
- HTS: High Touch Surfaces.
- ICU: Intensive Care Unit.
- IgG: Immunoglobulin G.
- IgM: Immunoglobulin M.
- IR: Infected Rate.
- IRB: Institutional Review Board.
- LTS: Low Touch Surfaces.
- MERS: Middle East Respiratory Syndrome.
- MERS-Cov: Middle East Respiratory Syndrome – Coronavirus.
- MoPH: Ministry of Public Health.

- MR: Mortality Rate.
- NCC: National Committee for COVID-19.
- NICU: Neonatal Intensive Care Unit.
- PCR: Polymerase Chain Reaction.
- PICS: Post Intensive Care Syndrome.
- PPE: Personal Protective Equipment.
- RR: Recovery Rate.
- RT-PCR: Reverse Transcriptase – Polymerase Chain Reaction.
- R/O: Roll Out.
- SARS: Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome.
- SARS-Cov-2: Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome – Coronavirus – 2.
- SR: Satisfaction Rate.
- SRp: Patient Satisfaction Rate.
- SRs: Staff Satisfaction Rate.
- SWOT: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats.
- WHO: World Health Organization.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

In December 2019, a novel coronavirus was first reported in Wuhan, China and then became a global pandemic in March 2020, as by the World Health Organization (WHO), as a result of an epidemic named ‘Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2’ (SARS-CoV-2) as by David Brewster in his consensus statement of airway management and tracheal intubation [1] [2] [3].

Several studies from China as by David B. and Ken Junyang Goh in his review of preparation of the intensive care unit for the COVID-19 pandemic, have highlighted a statistical approach and reported that a range of 15% to 25% of confirmed cases develop into Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS) and 20% to 30% into a critical illness [3] [4] [5]. Due to differences in the availability of tests and diagnostic resources, this level is difficult to interpret; it is therefore considered a critical condition for critically ill patients and may be considered emergency endotracheal intubation and mechanical ventilation to encourage recovery [3] [4].

According to the COVID-19 Guidelines by the Australian and New Zealand Intensive Care Society (ANZICS) on 16 March 2020, this viral outbreak is unexpected throughout the healthcare system, and particularly in Intensive Care Units (ICUs), and it is one of the non-routine challenges [6]. Therefore, the intensive care unit must prepare for the challenges of the epidemic by studying ways to prevent and deter the spread of the virus, through rapid diagnosis and isolation of not only suspected or confirmed patients, but also health workers and patients at risk from nosocomial infection, as by Jason Phua in his review of Intensive care management of coronavirus disease 2019 [7]. In other words, and according to the ANZICS’s Guidelines, the intensive care unit must be prepared to plan for this outbreak with an operational approach, to provide a safe working environment while protecting and supporting staff, and to identify and treat patients with COVID-19 infection [6]:

- Planning, to reduce routine intensive care demand, identify and increase the physical capacity of intensive care beds, and define basic equipment and manpower requirements.
- Providing a safe working environment and staff protection, considering the different levels of care such as illness, infection, engineering, management and administrative controls, as well as the appropriate Personal Protection Equipment (PPE) while transporting or acting with patients, with no denial of the need for care and good-being of staff, the need to manage the airways in COVID-19 patients and Code Blue rapid response.
- Identifying and treating patients, such as the COVID-19 Intensive Care test, while being mindful of the routine management of respiratory failure associated with COVID-19.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

ICU patients need ongoing medical supervision and support to keep their body active. For this reason, in the intensive care unit, special attention is paid to the skills, equipment and capabilities of medical and nursing services for patients with acute and unstable conditions.

Despite the importance of the challenges in the intensive care services and the partnership between private and public hospitals, there is still a lack of resources, infection prevention and management, protection and equipment.

For example, as by J. Xie, in certain stages of a pandemic, more than 75% of the equipment was exhausted without mechanical ventilation [8]. In this sense, the sustainability of a critical care unit has always been an important key in the entire health system, and the preparation must include not only the infrastructure of the ward, but also the protection of the team against the spread of infections. Therefore, one of the most important resources is having an experienced and trained intensive care team to care for high-quality critical patients. This rises important question: how to develop a local COVID-19 ICU pandemic plans, and how those plans will adopt a phased response based on the impact of the pandemic on the capacity of the ICU to meet daily operational needs?

1.3 OBJECTIVES

In our interventional study, we are focusing on the strategy, preparedness, measurements and challenges of the ICU setting, and looking at whether ICU services have been achieved in a sustainable manner, and suggest the need to:

- Prepare and implement rapid identification and isolation protocols and a surge in ICU bed capacity.
- Provide a sustainable workforce with a focus on infection control; by maintaining service capabilities and protecting healthcare workers.
- Ensure adequate supplies to equip ICUs and protect healthcare workers.
- Maintain quality clinical management.
- Maintain effective communication and coordination.

1.4 OUTLINE

This report consists of 5 Chapters:

- Chapter 1 is to introduce:
 - A brief background.
 - The problem statement which raises up the question of:” how to develop a local COVID-19 ICU pandemic plans, and how those plans will adopt a phased response based on the impact of the pandemic on the capacity of the ICU to meet daily operational needs?”
 - The objectives that aim to look at whether ICU services have been achieved in a sustainable manner.
- Chapter 2 is to:
 - Provide an overview of the previous literature review related to the topic.
- Chapter 3 is to:
 - Give an outline of the interventional research assessments that were followed in the study (pre-interventional, interventional and post-

interventional period). In addition to the site, participants, sampling, outcome measures, data collection, and data analysis.

- Chapter 4 is to:
 - Present the findings of this study which were obtained from the various analysis. In addition to the discussion that compares our study results with other studies.
- Chapter 5 is to:
 - Conclude the report with new recommendations.
 - Finalize the report with a future work.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter, highlight the national Lebanese experience facing the pandemic by focusing to assess and evaluate multiple strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats, in addition to a general overview concerning the challenges that faced the ICU COVID-19 without denying the importance of their preparedness and readiness by highlighting the importance of:

- Rapid identification and isolation protocols.
- Providing a sustainable workforce by maintaining capabilities and protecting healthcare workers.
- Ensuring adequate supplies to equip the ICU and protect HCWs.
- Maintaining quality clinical management.
- Maintaining effective communication and coordination.

2.2 NATIONAL LEBANESE EXPERIENCE

Since December 2019, an outbreak of COVID-19 has spread from China due to Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS Cov-2). In March 2020, the World Health Organization, and after the spreading of this virus to over 20 countries and regions around the world, characterized the global situation with COVID-19 as a pandemic [9] [10].

As of May 1st 2020, the total number of infections diagnosed with SARS-Cov-2 has reached over 3 million worldwide, resulting in more than 230,000 deaths. Reducing population morbidity and mortality were key public health goals through proportionate non-medical interventions, with an emphasis on protecting vulnerable people until effective vaccinations, treatments and medicines become available [11]. Since many researchers in their studies have

suggested that critically ill patients with COVID-19 have long-term physical, mental and other health problems, this underlines the importance of the ICU's readiness to deal with the challenges of this pandemic [12]. Due to the underlying data transmission of this outbreak, particularly in intensive care units, an infection control protocol must be implemented to treat confirmed and suspected MERS-Cov patients [13].

In Lebanon, on February 29, with the affirmation of the first case of COVID-19, the government inaugurated a "whole government response" through a public-private co-partnership, with the NCC orienting the plan and the Ministry of Public Health (MoPH) - beside other ministries-monitoring the implementation. In the face of significant resource constraints in the country, target has focused on early containment of offensive actions to create the capacity to respond to COVID-19 cases [14].

In addition to that, a patriotic strategic communication campaign was initiated four days after discovering the first case of COVID-19 [15]. The core strategy focused around overwhelming media outlets with data by healthcare experts: talk shows accommodated by doctors and public health professionals; public service messages displaying doctors were streamed by social media and television outlets in addition to governmental instructions around "keep at home" demands [15]. This induced an elevated awareness level on prevention and self-reported commitment to governmental guidelines implicating adhering to hand hygiene (96% adherence), bypassing crowds (90%) and adhering to stay-at-home orders (76%) [15].

Despite all applied strategies, Lebanon was facing confronts for the emerging pandemic. In addition to the economic and political disorders, the country is highly populated with 6.9 million residents [15]. The healthcare sector is crumbed with hospitals of different capacities [15]. Moreover, 80% of healthcare budget is disbursed on acute care in the private sector, leaving the public sector under-resourced. Besides, Lebanon depends significantly on abroad supply chains and has no regional manufacturing capacity to produce important COVID-19 fixtures, including N95 masks and ventilators [15].

According to the study done by J. Wang and Z. Wang, and based on the report done by UN-habitat, following is a SWOT analysis that refers to assess and evaluate multiple strengths (S), weaknesses (W), opportunities (O), and threats (T) that influence the general situation [16] [17]:

1. Strengths:
 - i. Health care and the health system are gradually improving.

- ii. Comprehensive advancement of the health emergency system.
- iii. The COVID-19 outbreak is rapid and effectively collaborated for interagency prevention and control.
- iv. Early adherence and compliance of Lebanese towards social distancing and safety measures.
- v. Interaction between the Public Health Ministry and Education Ministry to train students on preventive methods to encounter COVID-19.
- vi. Recruitment of a dedicated communication staff to monitor application of COVID-19 safety measurements.
- vii. Development of several training materials.
- viii. Utilizing several communications means to disseminate accurate information.
- ix. Training, simulation sessions and webinars were applied to healthcare workers

2. Weaknesses:

- i. The COVID-19 epidemic spread to many regions in a short period of time.
- ii. Lack of supplies and manpower.
- iii. Lack of awareness.
- iv. Long decades of distrust in the Lebanese government disabled Lebanese from communicating effectively with governmental authorities.
- v. Absence of previous Lebanese expertise in facing such pandemic conditions makes Lebanese communicative strategies towards COVID-19 aggressive rather preventive and requires more time compared to other countries.
- vi. Lack of dedicated surveillance system that unifies and gathers the data from whole regions in Lebanon thus leading to poor information disseminated and consequently to gap in the communication process.
- vii. Lack of enough human capital needed to complete the coding message of COVID-19 outbreak.
- viii. Lebanese diverse culture that demands various communications means; not all Lebanese sectors are familiar with advanced communication means, besides some possess aggressive mentality that refuse to obey to governmental and worldwide instructions related to COVID-19 restriction.

- ix. Lack of participation and coherence between Lebanese ministries which is probably due to political strife between Lebanese parties.

3. Opportunities:

- i. Foreign aids donated to Lebanon allowed government and media parties to invest more in applying effective communication cycle.
- ii. COVID-19 new exploration.
- iii. Delay of Lebanese infection by disease allowed it to learn from other nation expertise the adequate method of risk communication implementation.
- iv. Opportunities for education for infectious diseases.

4. Threats:

- i. Impact on the national economy: bad economic, political and security conditions present in the country are forcing high profile residents including healthcare professionals and important players in the communication task force against COVID-19 to immigrate leaving a gap in the performance and in the skills needed in such a war.
- ii. COVID-19 was unknown.
- iii. Impact on the daily life, work and psychology of the public.
- iv. Beirut explosion in august largely deteriorated the performance and put others out of service that affected significantly on application of measures against COVID-19.
- v. Beirut explosion mostly increased public contact and there was negligence to safety measures and precautions while aiding victims of explosion that boosted the number of infected cases lately.

2.3 PREPAREDNESS AND READINESS OF AN ICU COVID-19

The preparedness and readiness of a COVID-19 intensive care unit should be based on but no limited to:

A) Prepare and implement rapid identification and isolation protocols and a surge in ICU bed capacity:

Based on a specific triage protocol with efficient diagnostic test (pharyngeal swabs, or lower respiratory tract samples if applicable), in addition to a real-time reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) suspected COVID-19 patients are identified and isolated. Using a screening questionnaire concerning the travel and contact history, symptoms, and chest radiographs, patients were divided into risk levels for COVID-19 and were admitted to open wards, cohort beds, single or isolation rooms with negative pressure, respectively. Compared with other respiratory viruses, SARS-CoV-2 is considered more contagious when patients are symptomatic. However, in contrast to MERS and SARS [18], SARS-CoV-2 transmission can also occur in mild or asymptomatic disease [19]. This complicates case identification and contact tracking. Each health system must continually develop its own protocol and questionable case criteria to balance security while optimizing the use of resources [20]

It is important that sites to care for patients with critical illness must be identified as early as possible, taking into consideration the availability of oxygen ports, compressed air supply, clean water, and drainage systems [21].

B) Provide a sustainable workforce with a focus on infection control; by maintaining service capabilities and protecting healthcare workers:

B.1) Establish infection control measures:

Infection prevention and control is critical to protect both patients and HCWs [22]. HCWs are at great risk due to large amounts of aerosols and long contact with patients. In addition, the reproductive number for SARS-CoV-2 is higher compared to seasonal flu [23]. Like other viruses, SARS-Cov-2 can be directly or indirectly associated with droplet infection. Strict adherence to droplet and contact precautions including hand hygiene, eye care, safety and personal protective equipment (PPE) will be the main measures of infection prevention.

B.2) Education and re-training:

Education is essential for effective infection control, in-depth knowledge of healthcare professionals, and logistical and technical issues to be identified with the help of a conventional

or intensive care unit. Healthcare professionals should be trained to inspect, disinfect, and dispose of safe PPE, and retraining is needed from time to time to ensure staff availability and skills.

B.3) Segregation and surveillance:

HCWs should be separated to reduce the risk of cross-transmission. This allows for continuity of service if a team is quarantined.

Healthcare workers were tasked with recording temperature twice a day and submitting it to a centrally designed online platform. HCWs with fever or respiratory symptoms are also required to report to designated staff clinics, with COVID-19 testing and/or stay home instructions implemented as required.

B.4) Maintaining manpower capability:

The routine procedures and the infection control measures inside the ICU in a daily manner, highlight the necessity of additional manpower and time [24]. Due to the disease transmission, the workload will be highest than before, and the level of anxiety will be as huge in addition to mental and physical fatigue [25]. To mitigate this, an open communication channel and quickly dissemination of information were created, to keep employees updated on new developments. Psychological support resources and a helpline are also available. Sections of the public hospital have been converted into temporary accommodation for additional staff. Despite good intentions, “presidency,” going to work during illness is likely to increase the risk of transmission to the hospital [26]. The policy should ensure that healthcare workers need timely medical attention and stay home in the event of illness.

C) Ensure adequate supplies to equip ICUs and protect healthcare workers:

In the event of illness, the need for equipment and supplies, including personal protective equipment, increases exponentially. Priority should be given to the allied health, relief and support services, including pharmacies, laboratories and respiratory care services, to identify urgently needed equipment and drugs. To avoid market weaknesses, other channels must be identified [27]. The equipment supplies and pharmaceutical stocks should be integrated as much as possible in the hospital and between regional hospitals. Discarded items (e.g., used laryngoscopes and

bronchoscopes) may be preferable. For reusable items, it is important to ensure adequate capacity for prompt disinfection and sterilization.

Careful use of PPEs can help to maintain stock for infection control. Extended use and limited re-use of N95 respirators can be performed with appropriate precautions such as strict hand hygiene, reusable face shield over an N95 respirator [4].

Finally, large amounts of biohazard waste will be produced during the treatment of disease patients. Adequate waste management capacity is required to establish a safe environment for health workers and patients. Environmental purification appears to be beneficial in SARS-CoV-2; however, cleansing requirements should be consistent with hospital services to increase bed capacity [4].

D) Maintain quality clinical management:

There is always a misunderstanding concerning the clinical management of the critical illness caused by the COVID-19. The severity variation of this disease depends even if the patient is symptomatic or not.

The chest radiographs and computed tomography (CT-scan) are two radiologic modalities that help to detect the ground glass opacities and basal consolidation. However, even in patients who subsequently develop critical illness, the radiologic exam can be normal. In addition, the probability of critical illness for patients with advanced age (more than 60 years), can be more severe.

It was unclear whether a benign myocarditis can be caused due to COVID-19. Rapid neuromuscular blocking may be considered in patients with mild or severe ARDS. Without denying that the corticosteroids should not be used regularly because delayed clearance of viral cells is beyond research and treatment system.

E) Maintain effective communication and coordination:

During a pandemic crisis, communication and coordination must be made as effective as possible, with the aim of dispersing widely the information between all HCWs in a timely manner. Also as mentioned above, the intensive care team is a multidisciplinary team, so it should be close

to all efforts with nursing and infection control and other departments such as engineering, cleaning services etc., without denying the importance of the coordination with other local hospitals and medical centers with effective resource allocation [28].

Additionally, we can never overlook the importance of family engagement and the informed patient's consent, which are important in addressing concerns and managing expectations and setting precautionary goals in acute illness. To facilitate this communication with family members, it is necessary to involve the fields of public relations and social assistance, with the aim of reducing misunderstandings and building confidence in the health system [29].

Other additional considerations could be taken into consideration with the aim of preventing the spread of the virus and getting the workplace ready.

1- General Considerations to prevent the spread of COVID-19 at workplace (ICU COVID-19):

- Make sure that the work areas are clean and hygienic: surfaces (such as tables) and objects (like telephones, keyboards) should be cleaned regularly with disinfectants, as contamination of surfaces affected by employees is one of the main causes of the spread of COVID-19 [30].
- Encourage regular and thorough hand washing of employees, contractors and customers. Place hand rub dispensers in the work area. Be sure to refill these dispensers regularly and display hand washing advice labels as washing kills the virus and prevents the spread of COVID-19 [30].
- Promoting respiratory hygiene in the workplace: Display posters promoting respiratory hygiene and ensure that your workplace has face masks or tissue paper for those with a runny nose or cough at work, and closed sanitary disposal bins because good respiratory hygiene prevents the spread of COVID-19 [30].
- Promote a message that people should stay at home, even if they have mild symptoms of COVID-19: Display posters with this message in your workplace. Regular medical masks instead of N95 masks [30].

2- Getting the workplace (ICU COVID-19) ready:

- Develop a specific actions plan when someone becomes ill with COVID-19 at workplace: This plan should an isolated room from others to put the ill patient inside, taking into consideration that the number of people who contact this patient will decrease [30].
- Develop a contingency and business continuity plan: it will help to prepare the organization for the possibility of an outbreak of COVID19 in its workplaces. It may also be valid for other health emergencies.

Be sure that this plan addresses the mental health and social consequences of a case of COVID-19 in the workplace or in the community and offers information and support [30].

2.4 CHALLENGES THAT FACE INTENSIVE CARE UNITS DURING THE PANDEMIC

As mentioned in our problem statement in the previous chapter, in the COVID-19 intensive care unit, special attention is given to the skills, equipment and capacity of medical services and care for patients with acute and unstable conditions.

Despite the importance of the challenges in the intensive services and the partnerships between private and public hospitals, there is still a lack of resources, infection prevention and management, protection and equipment.

The following are some summarized tables concerning the challengers that faced the intensive care unit during the pandemic COVID-19 in many fields: Infection prevention, ICU infrastructure, Capacity, Staffing, and Triage [7].

Table 2-1: Challenges and Recommendations facing the COVID-19 ICU (Infrastructure)

	Recommendations
ICU infrastructure	
Airborne infection isolation rooms (AIIR) with negative pressure are not universally available, especially in resource-limited settings	Consider adequately ventilated single rooms

The intensive care units in most hospitals are not designed properly to deal with such a pandemic. Therefore, it will be harmful to patients, families, and staff specifically while working during respiratory pandemic. For this reason, a redesign should be considered in aim to minimize the exposure risk, so to ensure patients and HCWs safety, taking into consideration the following [13]:

- The COVID-19 ICU, should be in separate area, away from other ICU and neonatal ICU (NICU), dialysis, postoperative surgical unit...

- The COVID-19 ICU should have separate entry, exit and specific elevator with clear signage for direction.
- Clear signs as alerts for isolation rooms should be present.
- The bed capacity should increase by at least 20% when the number of patients increases.
- The COVID-19 ICUs should have a separate area for donning and doffing, preferably located in the anteroom at the entrance of ICU, in addition to a bathroom/sanitary area for HCWs to take showers after work before leaving the unit.
- The COVID-19 ICU should have a break room for staff post working hours to prevent a burnout. However, HCWs are allowed to rest after doffing.
- The COVID-19 ICU should contain adequate ventilated rooms with negative pressure.

The following is a suggested model of an ICU for airborne illness:

Figure 2-1: ICU model for airborne illness

Red arrow: Patient entry. Blue arrow: Healthcare worker entry. Black dashed arrows: self-sliding automated doors. 1. Red dotted area: negative pressure isolation area for confirmed COVID-19 patients, 2. Orange dotted area: buffer zone, need full personal protective equipment (PPE), 3. Red dotted area: suspected COVID-19

patients negative isolation area, 4. Common utility area, 5. Blue shaded area: PPE doffing area, 6. PPE donning area, 7. Yellow striped wall: full glass wall for patient observation.

Table 2-2: Challenges and Recommendations facing the COVID-19 ICU (Infection Prevention and Control)

	Recommendations
Infection prevention	
A global shortage of medical masks and respiratory protection threatens efforts to prevent transmission	Consider reuse between patients and use beyond the manufacturer-designated shelf life
N95 respirators that do not conform to the contours of the face may not provide the necessary protection	Conduct regular fit testing, preferably before outbreaks
Self-contamination while removing PPEs	Train on both the donning and doffing of PPE
Viruses on HCWs' mobile phones and hospital equipment can cause a nosocomial infection	Conduct surface decontamination and consider wrapping mobile phones in disposable specimen bags
Visiting the ICU creates a risk of contamination of visitors	Restrict or ban visits to minimize transmission; use video conferencing for

	Recommendations
	communication between family members and patients or health-care workers

A scientific approach “Infection prevention and control” (IPC), can be defined as the name suggests, to prevent and to control the infection. Prevent the infection, which means the act of stopping the infection from happening. Infection control is to control the infection that happened, to not increase the level of infection. In other words, it helps to maintain a stability of level of infection to be decreased. So, an infection prevention and control, is a quality standard and is essential for the well-being and safety of patients, staff and visitors. The hospital must collaboratively ensure the proper development, implementation and evaluation of the infection prevention and control plan that constitutes the focus of the standards. The aim of Infection Prevention and Control Policy is to ensure employees, patients and families that are protected against infectious diseases, so to minimise the risk of infection through the appropriate and timely isolation of a patient with a known or suspected pathogen or epidemiologically important organism and to ensure compliance with national policy and guidance related to infection prevention and control. It is not always possible to avoid nosocomial infections, but it is possible to limit the frequency and the severity in particular by the rigorous respect of the protocol of hygiene either for patients and families or for staff, in addition to surface disinfection and cleaning, physical distancing and respiratory etiquette.

Infection control facilities and air circulation:

- Provide appropriate hand washing and hygiene protocols, preferably with no touch sensors for hand washing, with adequate and enough sanitizers.
- The COVID-19 ICU should be separated from other units in order to minimize the risk of infection, in addition to a specialized room for donning and doffing.

- The used linen should be disposed of either in a water-soluble bag or in a container filled with 0.5% sodium hypochlorite.
- Provide telecommunication with ICU patients, such as a specific channel to avoid the necessity of physical visits and reduce cross-transmission risk.
- Corridors used for patient transport should be well ventilated and disinfected.
- COVID ICU should have enough airborne infectious isolation rooms (AIIR) for aerosol-generating procedures (AGP) whenever feasible. However, if there are not enough single rooms available, beds may be spaced at least one meter apart.
- Fresh air in the AIIR room should change from 6 to 12 per hour and be under negative pressure in relation to the environment (waiting room). A high-efficiency particulate air (HEPA) filter is connected to the atmosphere and recirculates at the outlet [13].
- Patient transportation shall highlight the importance of the staff and patient safety with the disinfection post-transportation [31].

Surface cleaning:

The surfaces can be divided into two groups: High-Touch-Surfaces (HTS), are the surfaces that are with frequent hand contact and need to be cleaned frequently; such as the door knob, bedrails, light switches. And Low-Touch-Surfaces (LTS), like floor, walls, curtains, that require cleaning less frequently [13].

Donning and Doffing:

The Donning and Doffing is a process that involve some steps in aim to take on and off the PPEs respectively. The PPEs include the following: goggles or face-shield, head cover, mask (surgical, N95...), gloves, coverall/gown, and cover shoes [13].

Table 2-3: Challenges and Recommendations facing the COVID-19 ICU (ICU Capacity)

	Recommendations
ICU capacity	
Surges in numbers of critically ill patients with COVID-19 can occur rapidly	Implement national and regional modelling needs for intensive care
Low-income and middle-income countries have insufficient ICU beds in general, and even high-income countries will be put under strain in an outbreak like COVID-19	Consider whether increasing intensive care provision is an appropriate use of resources; if so, make plans for an increase in capacity, including providing intensive care in areas outside ICUs and centralizing intensive care in designated ICUs
Increasing ICU capacity requires more equipment (e.g., ventilators), consumables, and pharmaceuticals, which might be in short supply	Pay close attention to logistical support and the supply chain; reduce the inflow of patients who do not urgently require intensive care (e.g., by postponing elective surgeries)
Ventilators are in short supply	Consider transport, operating theatre, and military ventilators

Many countries have not enough ICU bed while the number of COVID-19 cases was increasing. Controlling such situation, is difficult but possible. The number of expected cases could occur rapidly. Thus, a plan for increasing bed capacity of COVID-19 ICU, shall be provided in collaboration with the hospital, staff and government. For example, increase the number of beds inside an existing ICU, taking into consideration all protocols of infection prevention and control, in addition to increase the number of existing staff to avoid the burnout and to provide better services with better quality. Other plans could occur, such as remodelling of an existing unit/department, or transfer patients to a specialized hospital and ICUs [7].

Increasing the ICU capacity, need to increase not only number of beds, but also number of equipment to be used such as ventilators, pharmaceutical products, and the number of staff [7].

Table 2-4: Challenges and Recommendations facing the COVID-19 ICU (ICU Staffing)

	Recommendations
ICU staffing	
Increasing ICU bed numbers and workload without increasing staff could result in increased mortality	Make plans for augmentation of staff from other ICUs or non-ICU areas, and provision of appropriate training (e.g., with standardized short courses)
Risk of loss of staff to illness, medical leave, or quarantine after unprotected exposure to COVID-19, with a potentially devastating effect on morale, is high	Minimize risk of infection; consider segregation of teams and physical distancing to limit unprotected exposure of multiple team members, and travel restrictions to limit exposure to COVID-19, which is now global

	Recommendations
Staff are especially vulnerable to mental health problems such as depression and anxiety during outbreaks	Reassure staff through infection prevention measures, clear communication, limitation of shift hours, provision of rest areas, and mental health support

The coronavirus has a huge number of negative side effects on HCWs worldwide. The number of daily cases was increasing, and the ICUs were overwhelmed, this leads to significant workload and disruption of patient care. Therefore, the necessity of increasing the number of ICU staff was essential, taking into consideration the coordination between the individual teams, that contains doctors, nurses and many other HCWs and experts such as respiratory therapists, infectious disease specialists, experts in airway and other ICU procedures and preferably they have to be young with no medical history (comorbidities, pregnant or lactating women, immunosuppression). The team should be led by a senior that might be a leadership to encourage staff for working and building confidence. To avoid the burnout as much as possible, the schedule shall be presented as rotation to accomplish the night shifts and the day shifts.

As mentioned before, an essential goal while preparing an ICU COVID-19, is to prevent infection and to protect HCWs who are at a high risk of cross-infection. For this reason, an infection control specialist/coordinator, will be present to ensure that all HCWs follow the procedures of infection prevention and control [13].

Avoiding staff's burnout, the hospital should insure them medically, and the staff should undergo periodical temperature checks and screening for any symptoms of COVID-19. In case of developing any symptoms for one of the team, they should be prioritized for the testing.

Table 2-5: Challenges and Recommendations facing the COVID-19 ICU (ICU Triage)

Recommendations	
ICU triage	
ICUs can become overwhelmed as surge strategies might not be sufficient in an emerging pandemic like COVID-19	Consider implementing a triage policy that prioritizes patients for intensive care and rations scarce resources

A specific policy and procedure for triage should be implemented by all clinicians, and staff, complemented by a clinical decision support system, in aim to detect patient who are at probability to have the coronavirus. This triage procedure helps HCWs to be on the safe side to prevent the transmission of this virus [7].

According to the study done by Phua Jason [7], the following table, is a kind of summary of initial approach to critically ill patients with suspected COVID-19:

Table 2-6: Initial approach to critically ill patients with suspected COVID-19

2.5 POTENTIAL INTERVENTIONS

Based on the literature review, our potential interventions are listed as follows:

- Safe patient transportation.
- Family engagement.
- Improve the usage of telemedicine in order to decrease the rate of infection.
- Staff safety and conditions.
- Recruiting more staff aware, certified and able to take care of patients.
- Post ICU recovery care.

2.6 CONCLUSION

The ICU must be ready and well prepared for this overwhelming surge of patients and optimize workflows, without denying the importance of rapid diagnosis and isolation, clinical management, and infection prevention. Plus, the hospital administrators and policy makers must work with ICU practitioners to prepare for a substantial increase in critical care bed capacity. They must protect healthcare workers from nosocomial transmission and mental health issues that might be aggravated by the need to make ethically difficult decisions on the rationing the intensive care [7].

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Our approach for this study was to collect data and evaluate whether ICU services have been achieved in a sustainable manner. Then the data will be analyzed to find out the weaknesses, understand the causes of the issue. This was followed by the recommendation of process change to optimize care services.

3.2 THE COVID INTENSIVE CARE UNIT IN THE HOSPITAL

The COVID-19 Intensive Care Unit (contains 7 beds) is designed to provide a concentration of skills, equipment, and facilities for specialized medical and nursing care of patients who suffered from the novel coronavirus. Those patients need constant medical supervision and support to keep their bodies functioning. They may not be able to breathe on their own and may have multiple organ failure. Medical equipment sometimes performs the necessary functions for survival whether a person recovers.

The COVID-19 ICU team is a multidisciplinary group who, while maintaining high standards of patient care, is responsible for:

- Treating patients, their families, and friends with dignity, fairness, compassion and respect.
- Respecting the right of all patients to make informed decisions regarding care, treatment and their participation in education.
- Maintaining a commitment to the development, support, and recognition of the staff.
- Collaborating with all care providers.
- Respecting the cultural diversity within the community.

The mission is to provide outstanding patient care to improve the health of COVID patients, while being responsive to the individual needs of patients and health care providers.

ICU care thus requires a multidisciplinary team that consists of intensivists (clinicians who specialize in critical illness care), pharmacists and nurses, respiratory care therapists, and other medical consultants from a broad range of specialties including surgery.

3.3 METHODOLOGY

This document represents the methodology of an interventional study using also a mixed method: qualitative method using interview (**APPENDIX B**) and quantitative method using questionnaire (**APPENDIX C**), conducted at the Hospital launched from June 2021 to August 2021 into three consecutive periods: Pre-interventional (from June 1st till the mid of July 2021), interventional and post-interventional (from the mid of July 2021 till the end of August 2021) with the aim of providing better services since Lebanon was approaching high infected cases daily. So, our hypothesis was to find out whether COVID-19 intensive services were provided in a sustainable manner or not.

It is about community research and crisis intervention. These are often retrospective analysis specifically designed to assess the immediate impact of treatment or prevention and preparedness measures on this epidemic, with group-wide intervention (ICU staff) using specific tools such as instructional/educational practices and learning strategies that can be used throughout our process. This study was approved by the respective Institutional Review Board (IRB).

Therefore, we will work on a specific intensive care unit (COVID-19 ICU) with the aim of enriching our research with all necessary information about the behavior of the entire group in relation to the management and preparation of this service, as well as practical considerations and strategies, in addition to get an overview about the challenges and recommendations that may arise.

In this manuscript we have used:

- An interview (**APPENDIX B**):

- i. Purpose: Interview was applied to assess the level of the preparedness, readiness and healthcare services applied in Covid-19 ICU and through healthcare workers who were allocated certain responsibilities in their field. Consequently, we aim to detect the gaps and challenges presented with the aim of evaluating and optimizing those services.
 - ii. Sample size and background of participants: Intensivist Physician, Infection Disease Physician, head nurse ICU, head of quality department, registered and practical nurses, in addition to the infection control department.
 - iii. Duration of meeting: 30 - 45 minutes per interview.
 - iv. Duration for data collection: From June 1st, 2021, till the mid of July 2021 for the pre-interventional assessment and from mid of July till the end of August 2021 for the interventional and post-interventional assessment.
 - v. Language: English language was used in the interview.
 - vi. Inquiries developed: a range of 4 main parts divided into many questions were developed and asked to the interviewees:
 - A- General overview of COVID-19 ICU.
 - B- Preparation of COVID-19 ICU.
 - B- Clinical management.
 - C- Infection prevention, infrastructure, capacity, surge, staffing, triage.
- In addition to a quantitative questionnaire (**APPENDIX C**) used during the pre-assessment:
 - i- Purpose: In aim of assessing the level of the staff satisfaction inside the COVID-19 ICU.
 - ii- Sample size and background of participants: It is about 19 participants who work inside the COVID-19 ICU: 11 Registered Nurses and 8 Practical Nurses.
 - iii- Duration: This questionnaire will take approximately 10 minutes.
 - iv- Language: English language.

3.4 POPULATION

We are interested in understanding and managing the spread of COVID-19 in the intensive care unit of the hospital. Based on the results of the literature review, the articles provide key recommendations with key practical considerations and strategies used to prepare an intensive care unit to respond to the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as the challenges ICUs face during this outbreak, interventions that can be used to reduce the spread of COVID-19 and improve ICU care services.

Since the study focused on the interventions provided to patients in the COVID-19 intensive care unit, it is important to consider the following population: Head of department, Registered nurses, Practical nurses, Doctors, Head Nurse ICU, Infection department, Head of the Quality department in addition to the responsible committee.

3.5 OUTCOME INDICATORS

This work is an interventional study, using interventions and their impact on patients with the aim of optimizing the care services provided to those patients.

The initial parameters and variables used are shown in **Table 3-1**.

The variables shown in

Table 3-2, are used to derive the results (outcomes) of our study such as the Recovery Rate (RR), the Mortality Rate (MR) and the Satisfaction Rate (SR).

Table 3-1: Initial Parameters and Values

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICU beds. • Incubation Time. • Treatment Time. • Probability of development critical cases. • Recover of hospitalized individuals. • Threshold for interventions.
--

Table 3-2: Variables and Description

VARIABLES	DESCRIPTION
Days	Number of days after first infection
Exposed	Number of exposed staff
Infectious	Number of infected patients
Hospitalized	Number of hospitalized patients
Critical Cases	Number of critical patients
Death	Number of dead patients
Recovered	Number of recovered patients

The Recovery Rate (RR) denotes the percentage of the recovery rate of infected patients compared by the total number of infected patients inside the COVID-19 ICU and is expressed in Equation 1.

$$RR = \frac{\text{Number of recovered patients}}{\text{Total number of COVID-19 ICU patients}} \times 100 \text{ eq. 1}$$

The Mortality Rate (MR) is the percentage in which the patients die according to the total number of infected patients in the COVID-19 ICU and can be seen in Equation 2.

$$MR = \frac{\text{Number of died patients}}{\text{Total number of COVID-19 ICU patients}} \times 100 \text{ eq. 2}$$

The Satisfaction Rate (SR) is the percentage of patients and the staff are satisfied, and is shown respectively in Equations 3 and 4.

$$SRp = \frac{\text{Number of satisfied patients}}{\text{Total number of patients}} \times 100 \text{ eq. 3} \quad \& \quad SRs = \frac{\text{Number of satisfied staff}}{\text{Total number of staff}} \times 100 \text{ eq. 4}$$

3.6 DATA COLLECTION

Our data collection was based on three consecutive phases: the baseline assessment of the actual situation inside the COVID-19 ICU (pre-interventional phase), the interventional phase and the re-assessment (post-interventional) phase.

- In the pre-interventional assessment period, the categorization of data was collected from: An interview **APPENDIX B**) with the referred physician (intensivist) and the head nurse of COVID-19 ICU, with a small questionnaire (**APPENDIX C**) in aim to assess the existing situation, in addition to the protocols that are used by contacting the referred personnel (infection control department, quality department) and finally by using a SWOT analysis tool to determine the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats.

- In the interventional assessment period, which means the action plan period:

Based on our literature review, and comparing the result of the existing situation with the result of the literature, we conducted a certain number of interventions to be implemented inside the COVID-19 ICU with the aim of optimizing the care services:

- Safe patient transportation.
- Family engagement.
- Staff safety and conditions.

- Post ICU recovery care.

- In the post-interventional assessment period, data was re-classified using the same methodology and tools used in the pre-interventional assessment:

While comparing the outcomes before and after implementing the interventions, and by contacting the intensivist, head nurse, and other staff, the post-interventional assessment will be conducted to determine the differences before and after implementation.

3.7 DATA ANALYSIS

Data was analyzed to determine the differences before and after implementation of the specified interventions using an excel sheet document. We considered the period from the mid of July 2021 till the end of August 2021, was the interventional period to improve care services inside the COVID-19 intensive care unit. The data analysis was conducted to indicate the strengths of the unit, weaknesses, opportunities and threats with the newly implemented practices to optimize services.

3.8 CONCLUSION

This process improvement study looked at the challenges facing the ICU COVID-19. The subject serves to optimize the care services inside the COVID-19 Intensive Care Unit.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 INTRODUCTION

To evaluate the effectiveness of the practice change, results were compared before and after interventions implementation into three consecutive periods: pre-interventional assessment, interventional assessment and post-interventional assessment. This process improvement was promoted to optimize the care services inside the COVID-19 ICU through increasing patients, their families and staff satisfaction.

4.2 RESULTS

4.2.1- Pre-interventional assessment / Assessment of the existing situation:

A- General overview of COVID-19 ICU:

The manuscript illustrates the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the COVID-19 ICU highlighting the gaps and the positive points:

Table 4-1: SWOT Analysis of Initial Situation

Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
Interactions and meetings with other experts and professionals in this field	Economical and financial crisis inducing elevation of dollar value in black market thus affecting Lebanese	Meetings with professionals and experts in fields situated abroad.	Bad economic, political and security conditions present in the

	ability to import devices and equipment mainly PPEs and ventilators		country are forcing high profile residents including healthcare professionals and important players in the task force against COVID-19 to immigrate leaving a gap in the performance and in the skills needed in such a war.
Educated and skilled healthcare professionals and staff	ICU was not well prepared as bed capacity with negative pressure to face this pandemic despite that the number of patients was overwhelmed inside the Emergency Department and outside it.	Coronavirus was new, and gave new experience for nursing and open a new job offers abroad	The Beirut explosion largely increased public contact and there was negligence to safety measures and precautions while aiding victims of explosion that boosted the number of infected cases lately.

Recruitment of a dedicated communication staff to monitor application of COVID-19 safety measurements	Absence of previous expertise in facing such pandemic conditions	Foreign aids donated after august explosion	
Development of several training materials	Absence of rehabilitation center	Delay of Lebanese infection by disease allowed it to learn from other nation expertise.	
Utilizing several communications means to disseminate accurate information			

B- Preparation of COVID-19 ICU:

The preparation of the COVID-19 ICU was focused on infrastructure, supplies, staffing, patient's transportation, designation of isolation rooms, in addition to the infection prevention and control. Following is a detailed list about how the preparation takes into consideration all cited points:

- **Location, capacity of bed and basic equipment:** an old ICU was as COVID-19 Intensive Care Unit that contains four isolated rooms (four patients) at first, well prepared and ready with adequate negative pressure and basic equipment such as: ventilators, respirators, scope, syringe driver, infuser, paramedical materials, adequate PPEs and hand hygiene supplies. After that, the intensive care unit started by being enlarged and well prepared.
- **Staff care and wellbeing:** focusing on the care and protection of the staff is important to ensure a safe, sustainable workforce and to maintain high quality clinical care. It should be recognized that intensive care staff will likely have an increased workload with a heightened anxiety both at work and at home. In a period of social disruption, HCWs should be supported by appropriate measures to ensure that they can still attend work. This could include access on additional paid leave and the prime of COVID.
- **Communication and coordination:** effective communication is essential in such a pandemic. The information should be disseminated to the staff in a timely fashion. All necessary information was disseminated to all HCWs by email and hospital intranet. In addition to effective coordination between the ICU and other nursing departments, engineering and cleaning services, to harmonize efforts for a coordinated response.
- **Staff education and re-training:** education is very important with the aim of developing the skills and knowledge of staff with the aim of ensuring their readiness and proficiency. For this reason, sessions of doffing and donning PPEs, hand hygiene, isolation protocols, treatment and medications were given to staff on daily basis, to avoid spreading of infection and protect both patients and HCWs.

- **Staff surveillance and segregation:** HCWs should be segregated to reduce the risk of cross-contamination. This allows for service continuity, should a team be quarantined. If HCW is presented with fever or respiratory symptoms, he is required to report to designated staff clinics, with COVID-19 testing and/or stay home instruction implement are required for 14 days.
- **Family engagement:** effective communication with the family is very important to address concerns and manage expectations concerning life and the health of patients. Daily, the residents or attendees communicate with the family concerning the patient situation with family meeting whenever a critical case exists.
- **Rapid response and isolation protocol:** the rapid identification and isolation of a suspected COVID-19 cases, requires an efficient triaging protocol and access to rapid diagnostic testing. All patients are screened at the emergency department and outpatients' clinics. Based on a specific questionnaire concerning the travel and contact history, symptoms and preliminary investigations (chest radiographs/CT-Scan), patients are stratified into COVID-19 risk levels and admitted into ICU or cohort beds, multiple room beds or isolated negative pressure rooms.
- **Patient transportation:** all patients who require a transportation for other unit, have a specific transportation mode taking into consideration the patient, HCW, bystander safety in addition to the post-transportation decontamination. Once a patient is admitted to ICU, transport outside the unit should be limited. If transport is required, then coordination at a senior level is mandatory to ensure safety standards are maintained.
- **Staff conditions:** the necessity of increasing the number of ICU staff was essential, taking into consideration the coordination between the individual teams, that contains doctors, nurses and many other HCWs and experts such as respiratory therapists, infectious disease specialists, experts in airway and other ICU procedures and preferably they have to be young with no medical history (comorbidities, pregnant or lactating women, immunosuppression). The team should be led by a senior that might to be a leadership to encourage staff for working and building confidence. To avoid the burnout as much as possible, the schedule shall be presented as rotation to accomplish the night shifts and the day shifts.

C- Clinical management:

As mentioned before, the rapid identification and isolation of a suspected COVID-19 cases requires an efficient triaging protocol and access to rapid diagnostic testing. All patients are screened at the emergency department and outpatients' clinics. Based on a specific questionnaire concerning the travel and contact history, symptoms and preliminary investigations (chest radiographs), patients are stratified into COVID-19 risk levels and admitted into ICU or cohort beds, multiple room beds or isolated negative pressure rooms. In the case of in-patient, the decision will be taken by the Infection Control committee, by doing double PCR test in addition taking into consideration the symptoms and chest radiographs or CT-Scan. When the result of the two PCR tests is negative, the patient will not be isolated. In case of a negative PCR test, and the CT-Scan show a positive result, a lab test will take place for the IgG and IgM. According to these strategies, the committee will decide whether the patient should be isolated or not. The PCR tests are available inside the ICU COVID-19 and on a daily basis whenever it is required.

The following is a table that shows the outcomes' percentage during the pre-interventional assessment:

Table 4-2: Outcomes' percentage during the pre-interventional assessment

Outcomes	Pre-Interventional
Recovery Rate (RR)	64%: 16 patients over 25
Mortality Rate (MR)	4%: 1 patient over 25
Patient's Satisfaction Rate (SRp)	86.86 %: 22 patients over 25
Staff's Satisfaction Rate (SRs)	79 %: 15 HCWs over 19

Recovery Rate (RR) and Mortality Rate (MR): Based on an excel sheet **Table 4-3** that contains all COVID-19 ICU patients' name, age, weight, complications, diagnosis, room number, admission and transfer date, length of stay, and their evaluation, we found that 64% of patients have recovered and transferred, and 4% of patients were died.

Table 4-3: COVID-19 ICU patients list

Number	PATIENT'S NAME	Age	Weight	Complications	Room	Diagnosis	Covid-19	High flow nasal cannula	Intubation	Extubating	Admission Date	Transfer Date	Length OF Stay	Evaluation
1														

2														
3														

Patients' Satisfaction Rate (SRp): Based on the report done on July by the Quality Management Department, the overall satisfaction scored was 86.86% based on a specific questionnaire (survey) filled by patients to let them know that their opinion is very important and their feedback helps to provide quality services. The survey was divided into many categories as follows:

- a) **Admission and discharge process (77.14%):** Accurate and clear information upon admission on the expected cost of hospitalization in addition to the waiting time to get to bed.
- b) **Care from nurses (86.02%):** is affected sometimes by the massive nursing staff turnover and the cross-training and the delay in response time. Basically, it can be divided as following: explanation provided about patients' rights and responsibilities, education about patient's illness and treatment plan, education provided about pain management and prompt and effective response to the patient's pain, in addition to the length of time taken to response to the patient's call and the calmness around the room.
- c) **Medication management (83.03%):** pharmacists should play a vital role in providing different pharmaceutical care services to improve disease management through patient's assessment, ongoing follow-up and collaboration with other healthcare providers, to increase the satisfaction rate of medications management.
- d) **Consistency and coordination of care (85.29%):** it is important to enhance collaboration between physicians, nurses and other health care professionals to increase team members' awareness of each other's type of knowledge and skills, which leads to continued

improvement in decision-making, and will accordingly impact quality of care and patient satisfaction.

- e) **Treatment with respect and dignity (90.29%).**
- f) **General services (86.86%):** in terms of general services first how patients perceive the cleanliness of their care environment that ensure the high quality and effective care through a reduced risk of hospital acquired infections. Second, taking into consideration the use of visual cues and staff education that are effective in reducing noise levels.
- g) **Dietary services (73.73%):** arrangements for food preparation, distribution and serving should ensure that hospital food is of defined standards such as nutritional quality, balance, tastiness and temperature.

Staff's Satisfaction Rate (SRs): According to the questionnaire (**Appendix C**), that has been distributed to all the COVID-19 ICU staff (Registered and Practical Nurses), in aim to detect whether they are satisfied or not, we found that 79% of staff are satisfied based on the following result:

Table 4-4: Percentage of Staff Satisfaction (Pre-interventional assessment)

	Agree	Neutral	Disagree
I am confident that my organization will take all necessary steps to ensure a safe and healthy work environment during COVID-19.	89.6 %	5.2 %	5.2 %
I am satisfied with my organization's response to	79 %	15.8 %	5.2 %

COVID-19 and employee safety.			
The organization provides me with the tools I need to be efficient.	79 %	10.5 %	10.5 %
The organization supports my mental well-being.	31.6 %	26.3 %	42.1 %
I have clarified of my schedule and tasks.	63.1 %	21.1 %	15.8 %
I feel frustrated by my job.	31.6 %	42.1 %	26.3 %
Working with COVID-19 patients puts too much stress on me.	68.5 %	26.3 %	5.2 %
I feel burned-out from my work.	52.6 %	26.3 %	21.1 %
I deal very effectively with the problems of my patients.	52.6 %	42.2 %	5.2 %
I feel frustrated about being separated from my family.	58 %	5.2 %	36.8 %
My organization established infection control measures by ensuring adequate PPEs and safety measures with the aim of protecting the healthcare workers.	100 %	0 %	0 %
My organization maintain the manpower capabilities, staff surveillance, education and re-training.	79 %	21 %	0 %
My organization ensures effective communication and	46.1 %	48.7 %	5.2 %

coordination during COVID-19.			
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4.2.2- Interventional period:

Comparing the guidelines measure that take place with other guidelines, we will focus on some interventions approved by the department to optimize the care services inside the COVID-19 ICU as follows:

- Safe patient transport for COVID-19.
- Family engagement.
- Staff safety and conditions.
- Post ICU recovery care.

A- Safe patient transport for COVID-19: the hospital should be ready not only with the infrastructure, but also staff to be familiar with workflows. The spreading of infectious cases may be intentionally brought out of isolation rooms for many reasons. Intra-hospital transfer may be required from emergency departments to the wards, from the general floor to the intensive care unit and from the wards to radiology suites. During episodes of patient transport outside of isolation, potential breaches of infection control can occur. At the same time, when COVID-19 patients turn ill during transport, their management is exceptionally challenging as accompanying staff would be wearing the adequate personal protective equipment.

Mitigating the spread of COVID-19 should be a priority. That is why HCWs who handle the transport of COVID-19 patients must consider the following principles: first, early recognition of the deteriorating patient (patient safety). Second, HCW safety. Third, bystander safety. Fourth, contingency plans for medical emergencies during transport. Fifth, post transport decontamination.

The following are some principles and solutions for COVID-19 patient transport to be implemented with the aim of ensuring safe patient transport for COVID-19 and reducing nosocomial spread:

Table 4-5: Patient Transport Issues and Solutions for COVID-19

	Intra-hospital transport		Inter-hospital transport
	From EMD to ICU	For radiology scans	For advanced ICU services
Patient safety	Early transfer of deteriorating cases to ICU.	To minimize the need for scans, e.g. using bedside ultrasound and chest portable.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early transfer of deteriorating cases.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For deteriorating patients, to assess the need for intubation prior to transport. • To be accompanied by at least a doctor and a nurse who are able to handle emergencies during transport. • Continuous monitoring of parameters (blood pressure, pulse rate, pulse oximetry). • Continuous end-tidal CO2 monitoring in intubated patients. • Transport monitor should be equipped with defibrillation function or else a separate defibrillator is needed. 		
Safety of HCW and transport staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All transport staff should be mask-fitted for N95 respirators. • All transport staff to don full PPE prior to transport. • To put on surgical mask for patient during transport. • To avoid using open breathing circuits, or nasal oxygenation and non-invasive positive pressure during transport. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Endotracheal staff should be mask-fitted for N95 respirators. • All transport staff wear full PPE prior to transport. • To add on HEPA filters to

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To add on HEPA filters to endotracheal tubes if bagging is required via BVM. • To add on HEPA filters to expiratory limbs of the breathing circuits for ventilators. • Avoid unnecessary breathing circuit disconnection during transport. • Scans to be performed at the end of the day if possible, to allow for terminal cleaning of radiology. 	<p>endotracheal tubes if bagging is required via BVM.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To add on HEPA filters to expiratory limbs of the breathing circuits for ventilators. • Minimize endotracheal tube disconnections during transport.
Bystander safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To use a pre-planned dedicated transport route to each destination. • Security team to lead and ensure clearance of bystanders for the entire designated route ahead of the transport team. Security teams should wear surgical masks. 	
Rescue and contingency plans during transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To assess the need for intubation prior to transport. Intubation is best done in ICU under controlled settings with the intubating physician wearing PPE. • Prepare transport equipment and drugs in anticipation of medical emergencies, such as sudden cardiovascular collapse or hypotension. • Transport patient by using an adequate respirator. 	
Post-transport decontamination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dedicated housekeeping team in PPE to perform terminal cleaning of dedicated route and elevator right after transport. • Staff to doff PPE appropriately after transport. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dedicated housekeeping team in PPE to perform terminal cleaning of dedicated route and elevator right after transport.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staff to doff PPE in the nearest clinical area.
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B- Family engagement: Family centered care is recognized as a key component of high quality of ICU care. Health care providers are the most trusted information source. Despite the information that people can access via the internet and media sources, that info may have conflicting messages. That is why patients and family need to get information from sources they trust and from providers who are considering their health status and individual risk factors. For this reason and due to the workload, that present inside the COVID-19 ICU, innovative models of family engagement and support are needed urgently in the intensive care unit (ICU) during time of restricted visitation such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

One of the strategies that may be implemented, is to involve leveraging skills of persons outside of the clinical team such as resident, attending or fellow, dietician, social workers, or providers in specialties other than critical care as “communication navigators” in aim to provide additional support to families and minimize the misunderstanding and build the trust and confidence in the healthcare system without denying the importance of nurses inside the unit whom play an important role in the family engagement. The usage of this team in this role may have reciprocal benefits in terms of educational and experiential impact in addition to facilitating family engagement when families cannot be at bedside due to restrictions on visitation due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

The recommended intervention is intended to facilitate communication between the patient’s care team and the family member, to promote humanization of the patient and provide emotional support to the family. Navigators should identify a primary contact for the family by helping the family to determine the best platform for communication (phone, videoconferencing application or other...) and assist in overcoming any barriers to accessing communication platforms, including assistance with videoconference applications and designating preferred timing of contact from the clinical team. In addition, navigators facilitate communication as needed, such as helping families keep a list of questions to ask the clinical team, and providing

emotional support to families, allowing them to process their fears, anxiety and stress related to their loved ones' illness.

The following are the core components for a successful family engagement navigator program with their anticipated outcomes:

- 1- Policies: set forth expectations related to what types of information can be shared by navigators and specifications for maintaining privacy.
- 2- Navigator staff: are the people providing the communication support role in our setting.
- 3- Procedures: provide standardized and concise instructions for navigators to initiate contact, respond to difficult situations, and disengage when appropriate.
- 4- A resource guide serves as an important tool for navigators to access education materials.
- 5- Strategic organizational partnerships: between navigators and ICU teams are needed to ensure consistent and non-duplicative effort.
- 6- A communication strategy creates awareness of the navigator program among patients, families, and ICU providers.
- 7- Establishing a monitoring and evaluation plan and system allows for evaluating the extent to which the family engagement navigation program is achieving its intended objectives.
- 8- Lastly, oversight ensures that the program is being implemented in a standardized manner and is on track to achieve outcomes.

This program model is intended to provide a standardized approach for implementing a family engagement navigator program to deliver family-centered care, with:

1) The short-term goals of:

- Increasing communication encounters among family members, patients, and the healthcare team.
- Improving family knowledge about the logistics of communication during their loved ones' hospitalization.

- Increasing the use of humanization strategies such as the “get to know me” board.

2) The intermediate-term goals include:

- Family, patient, and provider satisfaction with the program.
- Increasing family engagement with decision-making.

3) Ultimately, the desired long-term outcomes of the family engagement navigation program are:

- Reduced stress disorders among family members including anxiety and post-traumatic stress disorder.
- Reduced stress disorders among patients.
- Alignment of patient care with their stated goals.

In aim of applying the communication navigator program, some strategies should be categorized as following:

1- Provide local technical assistance:

- Engage health information technology experts to assist if needed with communication resources.
- Enlist language services to provide support as needed.

2- Audit and provide feedback:

- Collect data and provide feedback to navigators and ICU clinicians on outcomes associated with the program including family experiences and outcomes.
- Regular debriefing meetings to enable identification and tackling of implementation challenges.

3- Develop educational materials/create online learning communities: Create educational resources and make them available for access online; documents amenable to continuous update as new knowledge and operations are available.

4- Conduct ongoing training: Navigators meet with a leader weekly to review cases and ensure procedures are being followed.

- 5- Promote adaptability: Clarify ways the navigator role can be tailored to meet individual needs and specify which elements of the innovation must be maintained to preserve fidelity.
- 6- Assess and redesign workflow: Monitor progress and adjust operational processes to continuously improve the efficiency and impact of the program. For example, we created an electronic health record note template to standardize information exchange.
- 7- Identify and prepare champion: Reach out to respondents' recommended champions and engage them with the program.
- 8- Engage community resources: Organize community resources such as free phone and Internet access from local providers.

C- Staff safety and conditions: There is no hospital that can keep its patients safe unless it keeps its health workers safe. So, the safety of HCWs is a step towards ensuring that health workers have safe working conditions, training and the pay with the respect they deserve. It is considered as a key to ensuring a functioning health system and a functioning society.

The following are some steps that are recommended to protect HCWs:

For employees who commute to work using public transportation or ride sharing, consider offering the following support:

- If feasible, offer employees incentives to use forms of transportation that minimize close contact with others (e.g., biking, walking, driving or riding by car either alone or with household members).
- Ask employees to follow the CDC guidance on how to protect yourself when using transportation (daily precautions steps: wearing mask, hand hygiene, avoid poorly ventilated spaces...).
- Allow employees to shift their hours so they can commute during less busy times.
- Ask employees to clean their hands as soon as possible after their trip.

Educate employees about steps they can take to protect themselves at work and at home:

- Encourage employees to follow any new policies or procedures related to illness, cleaning and disinfecting, and work meetings and travel.
- Advise employees to:
 - Stay home if they are sick, except to get medical care, and to learn what to do if they are sick (stay home, separate from others, monitor the symptoms, wear masks, clean touching surfaces, hand hygiene..).
 - Inform their supervisor before coming work if they have a sick household member at home with COVID-19 and to learn what to do if someone in their home is sick.
 - Wear a mask when out in public and when around people who do not live in their household, especially when other social distancing measures are difficult to maintain. Masks should not be placed on young children under age 2, anyone who has trouble breathing, or is unconscious, incapacitated or otherwise unable to remove the mask without assistance.
 - Wash their hands often with soap and water for at least 20 seconds or to use hand sanitizer with at least 60% alcohol if soap and water are not available. Inform employees that if their hands are visibly dirty, they should use soap and water instead of hand sanitizer. Key times for employees to clean their hands include and not limited to:
 - Before and after work shifts.
 - Before and after work breaks.
 - Before entering the patient room.
 - After exiting the patient room.
 - Before and after any medical act.
 - After blowing their nose, coughing, or sneezing.
 - After using the restroom.
 - Before eating or preparing food.
 - After putting on, touching, or removing cloth face coverings.
 - Avoid touching their eyes, nose, and mouth with unwashed hands.

- Cover their mouth and nose with a tissue when you cough or sneeze or use the inside of their elbow. Throw used tissues into no-touch trash cans and immediately wash hands with soap and water for at least 20 seconds. If soap and water are not available, use hand sanitizer containing at least 60% alcohol. Learn more about coughing and sneezing etiquette on the CDC website.
- Practice routine cleaning and disinfection of frequently touched objects and surfaces such as workstations, keyboards, telephones, handrails, and doorknobs. Dirty surfaces can be cleaned with Incidine Foam specific to disinfection. To disinfect, use products that meet the criteria for use against SARS-CoV-2external icon, the cause of COVID-19, and are appropriate for the surface.
- Avoid using other employees' phones, desks, offices, or other work tools and equipment, when possible. Clean and disinfect them before and after use.
- Practice social distancing by avoiding large gatherings and maintaining distance (at least 6 feet) from others when possible.

D- Post ICU Care for recovery: after the initial hospital stay, a provided specialized care can play an important and a critical role for patients. Most patients develop a post-intensive care syndrome (PICS) due to the long stay inside the intensive care unit, in addition to multi-system failure with lungs damage and other organs without denying the mental health disorders or brain dysfunction. These patients may have fatigue, muscle weaknesses, muscle pain, headaches and autonomic nervous system impairments such as palpitations and shortness of breath. The following is a suggested model of survivor center care that should be implemented to maximize the recovery of critical survivors.

A multidisciplinary staff member may include pharmacists, pulmonary critical care specialists, chaplains for spiritual support, ICU nurses, social workers, rehab specialists, intensivists because of the same burden in patients who have survived critical illness with COVID-19.

Mode of treatment that could be used is a video visit if a patient wants to have telehealth services, or by phone visits if patients are not equipped with a camera either on their phone or their computers in aim to support patients and their families and minimizing the risk of spreading the infection.

At the same time, patients at home are initially evaluated using objective measures that include respiratory rate, pain scale, fatigue scale and others. Based on the patient's result, a program will be developed geared toward respiratory mobility and activity of daily living (ADL) needs.

The program consists of two to four visits over a one-to-three-week time frame based on everyone's severity, needs and clinician judgment. The visits are stratified as follows:

- Visit 1: 2 – 4 days post-discharge; evaluation and service needs.
- Visit 2: 2 – 4 days post visit 1; evaluate progress and need to continue program.
- Visit 3: 7 – 10 days post visit 1; assess tolerance and progress exercise recommendations.
- Visit 4: 3 week post initial evaluation.

4.2.3- Post-interventional assessment:

The post-interventional assessment is conducted to determine the differences before and after implementation by comparing the rate of each outcome.

While comparing the existing situation with the implemented interventions inside the COVID-19 ICU, and by using the same tools to determine the rate of our outcomes, following is a table that shows the outcomes' percentage during the post-interventional assessment:

Table 4-6: Outcomes’ percentage during the post-interventional assessment

Outcomes	Post-Interventional
Recovery Rate (RR)	85 %: 17 patients over 20
Mortality Rate (MR)	10 %: 2 patients over 20
Patient’s Satisfaction Rate (SRp)	90.65 %: 18 patients over 20
Staff’s Satisfaction Rate (SRs)	84.3%: 16 HCWs over 19

Recovery Rate (RR) and Mortality Rate (MR): Based on the same excel sheet **Table 4-3** that contains all COVID-19 ICU patients’ name, age, weight, complications, diagnosis, room number, admission and transfer date, length of stay, and their evaluation, we found that: 85% of patients have recovered and transferred, and 10% of patients were died.

Patient Satisfaction Rate (SRp): Based on the same data collected during our pre-interventional assessment we found, according to the following results that 90.65% of patients were satisfied:

- a) **Admission and discharge process (78.3%).**
- b) **Care from nurses (91.27%).**
- c) **Medication management (85.4%).**
- d) **Consistency and coordination of care (87.02%).**
- e) **Treatment with respect and dignity (91.42%).**
- f) **General services (90.65%).**
- g) **Dietary services (72.65%).**

Staff's Satisfaction Rate (SRs): According to the same questionnaire (**APPENDIX C**), that have been distributed to all the COVID-19 ICU staff (Registered and Practical Nurses), in aim to detect whether they are satisfied or not, we found that 84.3% of staff are satisfied based on the following result:

Table 4-7: Percentage of Staff Satisfaction (Post-interventional assessment)

	Agree	Neutral	Disagree
I am confident that my organization will take all necessary steps to ensure a safe and healthy work environment during COVID-19.	92.7%	4.2 %	3.1 %
I am satisfied with my organization's response to COVID-19 and employee safety.	84.3 %	13.6 %	2.1 %
The organization provides me with the tools I need to be efficient.	80.4 %	11.3 %	8.3 %
The organization supports my mental well-being.	39.8 %	23.6 %	36.6 %
I have clarified of my schedule and tasks.	63.1 %	21.1 %	15.8 %
I feel frustrated by my job.	28.4 %	33.6 %	38 %
Working with COVID-19 patients puts too much stress on me.	72.1 %	23.7 %	4.2 %
I feel burned-out from my work.	63.8 %	15.1 %	21.1 %

I deal very effectively with the problems of my patients.	54.4 %	44.6 %	9.8 %
I feel frustrated about being separated from my family.	42.3 %	13.2 %	44.5 %
My organization established infection control measures by ensuring adequate PPEs and safety measures with the aim of protecting the healthcare workers.	100 %	0 %	0 %
My organization maintain the manpower capabilities, staff surveillance, education and re-training.	88.4 %	11.6 %	0 %
My organization ensures effective communication and coordination during COVID-19.	65.8 %	30.8 %	3.4 %

After comparing the results before and after implementation of the interventions, the following table is a summary of all values obtained during the study:

Table 4-8: Outcomes' percentage during the pre- and post-interventional assessment

Outcomes	Pre-Interventional	Post-Interventional
Recovery Rate (RR)	64 %	85 %
Mortality Rate (MR)	4 %	10 %

Patient's Satisfaction Rate (SRp)	86.86 %	90.65 %
Staff's Satisfaction Rate (SRs)	79 %	84.3 %

4.3 DISCUSSION

According to the **Table 4-8**, we found that:

Despite the elevation of the mortality rate by 6% (4% < 10%), the recovery in addition to the patients and staff satisfaction rates have been increased during the post-interventional period than the pre-interventional period respectively by:

- 21 % (64% < 85%).
- 3.79 % (86.86 % < 90.65 %).
- 5.3% (79% < 84.3%).

Our results concerning the recovery from COVID-19, the patients and staff satisfaction comparing pre-interventional assessment and post-interventional assessment, are consistent to the results of previous studies done by:

- The Australian and New Zealand Intensive Care Society, (March 16, 2020), and
- Jason Phua, (May 1, 2020) in Lancet Respiratory Medical journal.

4.4 LIMITATION

Although the interventional study was successful in optimizing the care service inside the COVID-19 ICU through increasing patients and staff satisfaction rate, in addition through increasing the recovery rate. This study had some limitations as follows:

- Our study was conducted with a limited time interval.

- Our study was conducted by having a limitation while partially using the telehealth service due to the economic and electric crisis.

4.5 CONCLUSION

In summary, and despite all the stress and the burn out that faced the staff, and despite the acceleration number of died patients, in addition to the economic situation the country was going through, we found by implementing the interventions inside the COVID-19 unit, that the organization have supported her staff and they have maintained together the quality of care by cooperating and well managing the situation over all the sides without denying the improvement of raising patients and staff satisfaction in addition to the recovery rate of infected patients.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

5.1 CONCLUSION

Based on the results of a retrospective, two group pre-interventional and post-interventional assessment, we found that focusing on a patient-centric strategy, may enhance the patient satisfaction. In other hand, while respecting and being always up to date to the specified policies and procedures of the organization, it could help to minimize the risk of contamination between not only patients, but also the healthcare workers and maximize their satisfaction that can help them to be more energetic during the working hours. Although our intervention was successful, we acknowledge that there are likely several other factors concerning our interventional study that contribute to patient and staff satisfaction that were not evaluated, in addition to other factors that may affect our outcomes. Further investigation is necessary to determine other factors such as workload, and environmental factors that have a direct impact on patient satisfaction, productivity and may affect the recovery rate with the waiting time for admission to the COVID-19 ICU. Additional interviews with health care providers as a step of the qualitative methodology processor or using the quantitative method could be helpful for our assessment and findings.

Recommendations for the hospital:

- Evaluate the effectiveness of the process and try to focus and improve other factors that may affect the care services inside the ICU.
- Create a culture of safety with clear coordination and communication between management and workers (avoid the procedure of blame).
- Allow staff to have enough time to organize their off-duty obligations and get sufficient rest and recovery.
- Minimize risk of infection; consider segregation of teams and physical distancing to limit unprotected exposure of multiple team members.

- Reassure staff through infection prevention measures, clear communication, limitation of shift hours, provision of rest areas, and mental health support.

Recommendations for the ICU staff:

- Acquire the knowledge and be updated about the current guidelines.
- Report any fatigue-related events or other to the manager to help prevent injuries and errors.

Recommendations for patients:

- Follow-up instructions delivered very well.
- Participate in specified educational sessions.
- Never hesitate to contact the referred physician when it is necessary.

5.2 FUTURE WORK

Further research is warranted to evaluate the long-lasting effects of our intervention focusing on:

- Implement the potential intervention that has not been implemented in this research.
- Replicate our type of interventional study in other Lebanese hospitals.
- Perform a qualitative study using interviews and a quantitative studies using questionnaire with healthcare workers (managers, secretaries, nurses, physicians...) including also other Lebanese hospitals.

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APPENDIX A

INFORMED CONSENT

I would like to invite you to participate in a research project by completing an interview. The purpose of this interview is to look at whether ICU services have been achieved in a sustainable manner, focusing on the strategies, preparedness, measurements and challenges of the ICU settings.

There are no known risks, harms or discomforts associated with this study beyond those encountered in normal daily life. The information you provide will be used to enhance and improve the effectiveness of the ICU and its preparedness and readiness for taking care of COVID patients. The study will involve mainly the ICU staff such as physicians (head of department), and nurses in addition, if it is possible the infection control and quality departments.

By continuing with the interview, you agree with the following statements:

- 1. I have been given sufficient information about this research project.*
- 2. I understand that my answers will not be released to anyone, and my identity will remain anonymous. My name will not be written on the questionnaire, nor will I be kept in any other records.*
- 3. When the results of the study are reported, I will not be identified by name or any other information that could be used to infer my identity. Only researchers will have access to view any data collected during this research, however data cannot be linked to me.*
- 4. I understand that I may withdraw from this research any time I wish and that I have the right to skip any question I don't want to answer.*
- 5. I understand that my refusal to participate will not result in any penalty or loss of benefits to which I otherwise am entitled to.*

6. *I have been informed that the research abides by all commonly acknowledged ethical codes and that the research project has been reviewed and approved by the Institutional Review Board.*
7. *I understand that if I have any additional questions, I can ask the research team listed below.*
8. *I have read and understood all statements on this form.*
9. *I voluntarily agree to take part in this research project by completing the following questionnaire.*

Date	Name	Position	Signature

APPENDIX B

ASSESSMENT OF EXISTING SITUATION

Optimizing Care Services in ICU COVID-19

This interview is used to accomplish research study. It aims to:

- 1- Prepare and implement rapid identification and isolation protocols and surge in bed capacity inside the ICU.*
- 2- Provide a sustainable workforce by focusing on the infection control to maintain service capabilities and to protect healthcare workers.*
- 3- Maintain adequate quality in clinical management with effective communication and coordination.*

Pre-interventional assessment (Assessment of the existing situation)

- A- General overview of COVID-19 ICU.
- B- Preparation of COVID-19 ICU.
- C- Clinical management.
- D- Infection prevention, infrastructure, capacity, staffing, triage.

A- General overview of COVID-19 ICU: (2 Questions)

1. What is the mission, vision and goals of the COVID-19 ICU?
2. What are the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats that faced the COVID-19 ICU? (SWOT Analysis).

B- Preparation of COVID-19 ICU: (3 Questions)

1. How have you planned to make the ICU adequate and well prepared?

- Physical capacity
 - Basic equipment
 - Manpower requirements
2. Does the ICU preparation was focused on infrastructure, supplies, staffing, patient's transportation, designation of isolation rooms, infection prevention and control? *Here are some examples that may help:*
- Location.
 - Entrance and access.
 - Capacity of beds.
 - Team and its encouragement.
 - Communication and coordination.
 - Optimizing the role of healthcare workers.
 - Maintaining manpower capabilities.
 - Staff education and re-training.
 - Staff surveillance and segregation.
 - Family engagement.
 - Rapid response and isolation protocol.
3. The following are some guiding principles for airway management of patients with COVID-19:
- Intensive training.
 - Early interventions.
 - Vigilant infection control.
 - Meticulous planning.
 - Efficient airway management process.
 - Clear communication.
 - Standardized practices.

According to those principles, have the recommendations been well developed with the goal of maintaining staff safety while providing timely, efficient and effective airway management?

C- Clinical management: (5 Questions)

1. Can you easily distinguish COVID patients from other severe communities acquired pneumonia? How?
2. How many ICU patients suffered from acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) and critical illness? What were the actions to be taken?
3. How did you manage the lack of resources inside your ICU?
4. Are the PCR assays always available in the ICU with adequate and sufficient test of diagnostic?
5. Does the sensitivity of PCR assays for critically ill patients is well known?

D- Infection prevention, infrastructure, capacity, staffing, triage: (12 Questions)

1. Can the ICUs become overwhelmed as surge strategies and not sufficient in an emerging pandemic such as COVID?
2. Does a shortage of PPEs and respirators threaten effort to prevent transmission in the ICU?
3. Does self-contamination happen while removing the PPEs?
4. Can a viable virus on HCW's mobile phones and hospital equipment cause nosocomial transmission?
5. Can an ICU visits pose a risk of infection to visitors?
6. Are the Airborne Infection Isolation Rooms (AIIR) available with adequate negative pressure?
7. What if surges in the number of critically ill patients with COVID occur rapidly?
8. What if the number of patients with COVID increase with no availability of staff?
9. Does the risk of loss of staff to illness, medical leave or quarantine after unprotected exposure high?
10. Are staff vulnerable to mental health problems such as depression and anxiety during the outbreak?
11. Are hand hygiene protocols and sanitizers clearly identified and applicable?

12. How are you supporting HCWs at individual levels? *For example:*

- Mental health.
- Infection prevention and control.
- Incentives.
- Occupational health and safety.
- Work conditions.

APPENDIX C

STAFF SATISFACTION QUESTIONNAIRE

Optimizing Care Services in ICU COVID-19

This survey is used to accomplish the research study. It aims to assess staff satisfaction inside eh COVID-19 ICU. This questionnaire will take around 10 minutes of time.

1- Gender:

Male

Female

2- Age:

< 20

20 – 40

41 – 60

> 60

3- Marital status:

Single

Engaged

Married

Divorced

4- Job title (Position):

Intensivist

Infection Disease Physician

- Head Nurse (HN)
- Registered Nurse (RN)
- Practical Nurse (PN)
- Other:

5- Years of experience:

- < 1 year
- 1 – 5 years
- 6 – 10 years
- > 10 years

6- I am confident that my organization will take all necessary steps to ensure a safe and healthy work environment during COVID-19.

- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree

7- I am satisfied with my organization's response to COVID-19 and employee safety.

- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree

8- The organization provides me with the tools I need to be efficient.

- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree

9- The organization supports my mental well-being.

- Agree

- Neutral
- Disagree

10- I have clarified of my schedule and tasks.

- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree

11- I feel frustrated by my job.

- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree

12- Working with COVID-19 patients puts too much stress on me.

- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree

13- I feel burned-out from my work.

- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree

14- I deal very effectively with the problems of my patients.

- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree

15- I feel frustrated about being separated from my family.

- Agree

- Neutral
- Disagree

16- My organization established infection control measures by ensuring adequate PPEs and safety measures with the aim of protecting the healthcare workers.

- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree

17- My organization maintain the manpower capabilities, staff surveillance, education and re-training.

- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree

18- My organization ensures effective communication and coordination during COVID-19.

- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree